
Guidelines and Style for IRRN Contributors

To improve communication and to speed the editorial process, the editors of the International Rice Research Newsletter (IRRN) request that contributors use the following guidelines and style:

Style

- Use the metric system in all papers. Avoid national units of measure (such as cavans, rai, etc.).
- Express all yields in tons per hectare (t/ha) or, with small-scale studies, in grams per pot (g pot) or grams per row (g/row).
- Define in footnotes or legends any abbreviations or symbols used in a figure or table.
- Place the name or denotation of compounds or chemicals near the unit of measure. For example: 60 kg N/ha; not 60 kg/ha N.
- The US dollar is the standard monetary unit for the IRRN. Data in other currencies should be converted to US\$.
- Abbreviate names of standard units of measure when they follow a number. For example: 20 kg ha.
- When using abbreviations other than for units of measure, spell out the full name the first time of reference, with abbreviations in parenthesis, then use the abbreviation throughout the remaining text. For example: The efficiency of nitrogen (N) use was tested. Three levels of N were ... or Biotypes of the brown planthopper (BPH) differ within Asia. We studied the biotypes of BPH in ...
- Express time, money, and measurement in numbers, even when the amount is less than 10. For example: 8 years; 3 kg/ha at 2-week intervals; 7%; 4 hours.
- Write out numbers below 10 except in a series containing some numbers 10 or higher and some number lower than 10. For example: six parts; seven tractors; four varieties. But There were 4 plots in India. 8 plots in Thailand, and 12 plots in Indonesia.
- Write out all numbers that start sentences. For example: Sixty insects were added to each cage; Seventy-five percent of the yield increase is attributed to fertilizer use.

Guidelines

- Contributions to the IRRN should generally be based on results of research on rice or on cropping patterns involving rice.
- Appropriate statistical analyses are required for most data.
- Contributions should not exceed two pages of double-spaced, typewritten text. Two figures (graphs, tables, or photos) per contribution are permitted to supplement the text. The editor will return articles that exceed space limitations.
- Results of routine screening of rice cultivars are discouraged. Exceptions will be made only if screening reveals previously unreported information (for example, a new source of genetic resistance to rice pests).
- Announcements of the release of new rice varieties are encouraged.
- Use common — not trade — names for commercial chemicals and, when feasible, equipment.
- Do not include references in IRRN contributions.
- Pest surveys should be quantified with data (% infection, degree of severity, etc.).

Genetic evaluation and utilization

OVERALL PROGRESS

Gibberellin response of japonica-indica hybrids in Korean rice cultivars

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The recent rapid increase in rice yields in Korea is based mainly on the successful release of new japonica-indica hybrid cultivars. These cultivars were bred using IRRI semidwarf lines, whose semidwarf gene comes from Dee-geo-woo-gen and is believed to limit gibberellin (GA) biosynthesis. Hence, these new hybrid cultivars should respond more to applied GA.

To check this effect, we compared the response to GA of the second leaf sheaths of japonica-indica hybrid cultivars with that of some japonicas and indicas. The cultivars used were japonicas: 1) Milseong, 2) Milyang 15, 3) Mankyeong, 4) Koshiji-wase, 5) Nipponbare, 6) Eiko; indicas: 7) Early Tall Peta, 8) Dee-geo-woo-gen, 9) Mao-tsu-tao, 10) Kaladumai, 11) Century Patna 231, 12) Dular, 13) CO 13, 14) Hawaragepoek; and hybrids: 15) Tongil, 16) Yushin, 17) Milyang 21, 18) Milyang 23, 19) Milyang 30, 20) Milyang 42, 21) Suweon 258, 22) Suweon 264, 23) Nopung.

The results (see figure) indicated a negative correlation between the length of the second leaf sheaths and the

Relationship between length of second leaf sheath (LSLS) and response to gibberellin (1 ppm) of japonica, indica, and japonica-indica hybrid rice cultivars. ○ = japonica, ▼ = indica, ● = japonica-indica hybrid. For numbering of cultivars, see text.

response to GA. Most japonicas had short leaf sheaths and high GA response, whereas indicas, except Dee-geo-woo-gen which possesses a semidwarf gene, had long leaf sheaths and low GA response. The hybrid cultivars had short leaf sheaths but showed different reactions — one gave a very high GA response and the other the lowest response. The first group probably possesses a semidwarf gene of Dee-geo-woo-gen which limits GA biosynthesis; the latter probably possesses some genes that lack the site of action of GA.

Japonica-indica hybrids belonging to the latter group are important as new dwarf gene sources for rice breeding, although the genetic basis for such is unknown. ■

PY1 or Pudukai Ponni — a new rice for late samba

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The northeast monsoon period (Sep-Oct to Dec-Jan) in the Coromandal coastal belt of Pondicherry is characterized by low temperatures (25-30°C), reduced

sunlight duration (5.5-8.3 h/day), monsoon cloudiness, and high rainfall (927-1,144 mm in 50-53 rainy days). Pest incidence is heavy during the period. Despite such unfavorable conditions, almost 70% of the cultivable area in the Union Territory of Pondicherry is under monsoon rice because of heavy monsoon showers and excessive moisture.

Among the medium-duration rice var-

ieties released for general cultivation, only Mashuri and IR20 are adaptable.

Mashuri, called Ponni locally, has fine grain, yields 4-4.5 t/ha, and matures in 130 days. But it is highly susceptible to pests. Farmers in the region need a variety with the desirable traits of Mashuri plus high yield potential and pest resistance. With such a variety as the objective, Mashuri and IR8 were crossed and their segregating progenies were studied. A progeny line, P162, was released as PY1 Pudukvai Ponni for general cultivation in 1979.

PY1 is a medium-duration variety that grows to 110 cm (Ponni or Mashuri grows to 120 cm). Its tillers are erect and compact, averaging 8 productive ones/hill. PY1 is tolerant of lodging and pests, and matures in 130 days. The color of the ripening spikelet is gold to

Mean yield of PY1 Pudukvai Ponni compared with that of IR20 and Mashuri (Ponni) in the monsoon (Sep-Feb) season in Pondicherry Region, India.

Type of trials	Year	Yield (t/ha)		
		PY1	IR20	Mashuri (Ponni)
Trials at research stations	1977	5.1	3.5	3.5
	1978	4.8	1.9 ^a	4.1
	1979	6.5	4.1	5.3
Adaptive trials in farmers' fields	1977	6.0	4.2	4.8
	1978	4.7	4.3	4.3
	1979	5.5	4.8	—
General mean		5.4	4.2	4.4
		Yield difference (%) over IR20		
		+28.6	0	+4.8
		Yield difference (%) over Mashuri		
		+22.8	-4.6	0

^aSeverely affected by brown planthopper and virus; omitted in arriving at general mean.

brown. PY1's density and panicle length are almost identical to those of Ponni. The length-breadth ratio of PY1 grain is 3.0; that of Ponni is 3.2. The 1,000-grain weight of PY1 is 17.2 and that of Ponni

is 16.2 g. PY1's yields average 5.4 t/ha (29% higher than that of IR20, and 23% higher than that of Mashuri) (see table). ■

PY2 or Punithavathi — an early-maturing, fine-grained rice

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The Union Territory of Pondicherry, India, is an area of intensive rice culture under a rice-based multiple cropping system. Varieties up to 115 days in duration are raised during the dry seasons—January-April (*navarai*) and May-September (*sornavari*).

Because the duration of the varieties raised is 110-115 days, they cannot be fitted into the rice-based multiple cropping pattern. These varieties postpone planting subsequent crops on time. In addition, the farmers prefer fine-grain rice varieties with high yield potential because the traders and consumers prefer fine varieties.

All the short-duration varieties raised now during *navarai* and *sornavari* have coarse grains (long bold or short bold). Therefore, rice breeding at the Farm Science Centre seeks to develop varieties of less than 100 days duration with fine grain and high yield to profitably fit the rice-based multiple cropping system, where raising crops from January to September depends upon lift irrigation. This led to the identification of the

Mean yield level of PY2 or Punithavathi rice variety in the Pondicherry region, India.

Situation	Yield (t/ha) in				Mean
	1978 kharif (sornavari, May-Sep)	1979 rabi (navarai, Jan-Apr)	1979 kharif (sornavari, May-Sep)	1980 rabi (navarai, Jan-Apr)	
Rice Research Station	3.4 ^a	4.9	5.4	4.5	4.5
Adaptive trials at farmers' holdings	—	4.7	4.7	4.5	4.1
Demonstration in farmers' holdings	—	—	5.0	4.8	4.9
All India Coordinated Rice Improvement Project trials (IET6972)	—	—	4.9	—	4.9
Lab to Land Program				4.8	4.8
Mean	3.4	4.8	4.8	4.6	4.8
Local check	1.8	2.5	4.2	—	—
	(CO 39)	(CO 39)	(ADT31)		

^aTrial was severely affected by brown planthopper.

P1275 line, which was released as PY2 (Punithavathi) in February 1980.

PY2 (Punithavathi) is a derivative from the cross between Kannagi (Puza 2-21) and Cult. 2032. It is a medium-dwarf variety like IR20. It grows to 90 cm in height and is resistant to the brown planthopper under field conditions. Tillers are erect, compact, and resistant to lodging. It matures in 95 days under transplanted conditions. The boot leaf is slightly broad, erect, and late in senescence. The grain type is fine (short slender) like TKM6 with the length-breadth ratio of 3.96. Grain weight is 18.5 g/1,000 grains and the rice is translucent white. The ripening color of the

glume is straw. The spikelet is green tipped. Punithavathi's average yield is 4.75 t/ha — minimum and maximum being 3.38 and 5.37 t/ha, respectively — superior to those of early and short-duration varieties tested (see table). ■

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